

THE FORTRESS-CITIES ON THE LEFT BANK OF THE AMUDARYA IN THE 19TH CENTURY

Otegenov Khakimbay Maksetbaevich

Karakalpak State University named after Berdak, doctor of philosophy in history.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11004757>

Abstract. This article talks about the fortress-cities on the left bank of the Amudarya in the 19th century, the fortress-cities of the Karakalpaks during the research period.

Key words: Island tribes, fortress-cities, historians, archaeological and ethnographic, black houses

ГОРОДА-КРЕПОСТИ НА ЛЕВОМ БЕРЕГУ АМУДАРЬИ В XIX ВЕКЕ.

Аннотация. В статье рассказывается о городах-крепостях на левом берегу Амударьи в XIX веке, городах-крепостях каракалпаков в период исследования.

Ключевые слова: островные племена, города-крепости, историки, археолого-этнографические, черные дома.

In the 19th century, fortress-cities and settlements were established on the banks of the Arol, in the lower reaches of the Amudarya, in the river branches, in geographically favorable places. Information about these cities is given in the works of Khiva historians Munis, Ogahi, and in the archive documents of the Khans of Khiva. It is also found in folklore and Karakalpak literature of the 19th century (Kunkhoja, Ajiniyaz, Berdaq, O'tesh, etc.).

Such brief information can be found in reports and travel diaries of members of scientific and military missions (D. Gladishev, I. Muravin, G.P. Danilevsky, M.N. Galkin, N. Karazin, A.V. Kaulbars, V.V. Grigorev, N. I. Veselovsky, M.G. Kun, A. Vamberi, etc.), they are also shown on foreign maps of the XVIII-XIX centuries.

S.P. Researchers who participated in the Khorezm archaeological and ethnographic expedition led by Tolstov made a great contribution to the study of the history of Karakalpaks.

Academician S. Kamalov studied archival documents on the history of Karakalpaks from the period called "Yangidaryo", as well as records recorded during field research conducted in the area. In the 70s of the 20th century, local ethnographers were mainly Kh. In the works of Esbergenov, the remains of villages and settlements were studied.

Archaeologist M. Mambetullaev, G'. Khojanliyazov, historian O. Yusupov systematically studied the cities and fortresses of the Karakalpaks in the XVII-XIX centuries, and the results of their research were published.

GUDAYBERGEN – FORT. Gudaybergen - the fortress was built in the desert zone, on the bank of the Kuhna river, in the territory of the Kūngirot district. The information that the city was built by the governor of Khiva, Gudaybergen, has been preserved. T. A. According to research conducted by Zhdanko in 1957, its walls were heavily damaged and in these places, brick blocks can be identified. You can see the large opening in the south wall and the remains of the building associated with the gate. The city is surrounded by a thatched fort wall. Its towers were also broken.

Remains of mud-built places are not preserved in it. Like other cities, people lived in black houses.

According to historical and oral information, the Kudaybergen castle was built in the 19th century, and the people there moved to the New Castle soon after the river water dried up.

According to the informants, this fortress is located on the border of Shūmanoy and Kanlikūl districts. According to the informants, the settlement was built in 1878 on the bank of the ancient Kiyatjargan river of Amudarya. The walls of the Kudaybergen fortress were rebuilt from pakhsa blocks. The name of Qudaibergan biy Mehrem is mentioned in Khiva archive documents [2,103]. NEW CASTLE (Sho'manoi). There are three monuments on the left side of the river in the name of "New Castle", one of the fortress-cities of the Karakalpaks. New Castle or Kūhna Shomanoi Castle is now A. A farmer named Musaev is located on the territory of the farm. The castle was built on a flat land on the old "Ilakali" hillock. A new channel was dug on the eastern side of the monument. In April 1983, under the leadership of Candidate of History Jumabay Ubbiniyazov, inspection work was carried out on the New Castle, where the caravan route to Kungirat or Khojeli passed, and its picture and schematic plan were taken. The monument was built in a quadrangular shape, and the remains of the cell were kept inside it. The height of the castle is 2.5-2.7 meters, the length is 250-350 meters. Reeds and red bells fell on the straw nails on the south side. There are 16 holes in the wall on this side. They are properly constructed. The size of the firing points is 18x22 cm. trapezoidal, 90 cm long. In several rooms inside the city, there are stairwells where books and other items are stored. The old gate of the castle was built, but now their remains are not preserved.

There are the following legends about the appearance of the new fortress.... A new fortress was built during the time of Khan Madreim of Khiva. In this fortress, Abdireyim from Khiva was a rich governor, he kept volunteer troops, collected taxes from residents in this fortress, collected tolls from travelers due to the fact that there was a road and passage near the fortress. The people will never forget the bravery of the hero Tilevmurat, who protected the new castle from the enemy.

In written sources, in the works of tourists and Khorezm historians of the last century, he mentions the New Castle as a newly created fortress on the other side of the Amudarya. The appearance of this fortress is first mentioned in the manuscript book of Muhammed Riza Ogahi called "Gulshani State". In 1859, Khiva Khan was returning from a march to Kunghirot, when he got tired on the way and went to the Chanak Sheikh Garden. There are rooms for the king. The garden in New Castle was surrounded by New Walls, these lands were named after Nurulla Boy.

From this we can see that a new city was created in the rich land of Nurulla on the road of Kūngirot, and it was built by the Khan of Khiva.

The "New Castle" is mentioned in the manuscript "Shajarayi-Khorazmshahi" by the historian of Khorezm Bayani. The uprising of the people of Kungirat in the 50s of the last century caused great danger to Khiva Khan. In order to cut off water from the people of Kungiro, Khiva Khan put a barrier on the Amudarya rivers and started to build a fortress-city on the roads and crossings. The appearance of the new city-fortress was initially formed by Khiva as a military fortress due to the Kungirat uprising of the Karakalpaks in 1858-1859. According to Bayani, caravans were coming to the "New Castle". So, the former military fortress turned into a city, then a commercial center.

Tourist Mirzo Abdurakhman (1873) states that one of the most popular places of Karakalpaks is "New Castle". Participant of Khiva campaigns in 1873 M. Alikhanov-Avarsky also

mentions the "Dzhana-kala" fortress. Russian researcher A. V. Kabulbars (1873) shows that agriculture is well developed along the Shūmanoy canal, and that there are yutroks in these lands.

Girshfeld and Galkin, Stepkevich and others mentioned about the settlements of the new city Shūmanoi.

We see that in the second half of the 19th century, the New City was a commercial and administrative center in the Shūmanoy district. In the 60s of the 19th century, after the Kūngirot crisis, Khiva Khan built the New Castle for the purpose of centralizing and strengthening the control and management of scattered Karakalpaks.

The construction of the fortress on one branch of the Amudarya and on the coast also meets the requirement of military fortification. In 1894-1899, the water of the Shūmanoy stream returned, and the inhabitants of the New City began to leave the fortress due to lack of water. The fortress of the New City (Kūhna Shūmanoi) was built by the Khan of Khiva, the life of the fortress corresponds to the years 1859-1899. NEW CASTLE (Konlikūl). On the left branch of the Amudarya, there are fortress cities named New Castle on the banks of Begjab and Ilaqali rivers.

Monument archaeologists S. P. Tolstov, T. A. Researched by Jdanko. On the walls of the new city fortress there are watchtowers, towers, shooting gezer (a place adapted for shooting arrows in three directions), a deep trench was dug around the walls-fortress, filled with water, and strengthened so that the enemies could not pass through. It is located in the territory of Qonlikul district, measuring 97x113 m, in the shape of four corners. The sides are focused on the main points. A gate was built on each of the middle walls. Pakhsa blocks are installed on the walls. On the outer edge of the upper wall there are decorative pits 30 cm apart. They mean a partition with a width of 8-10 cm and a height of 55-65 cm without piercing the wall. There are half-round towers in the corners of the castle. There are half-round towers in the corners of the castle. All the walls, from the corners to the gates, have buttresses. The walls are equipped with holes similar to holes, which are more than half a meter above the floor; Between the northern and western walls there are three openings. The construction of the new fort was built for the station road between Khojaly-Kungiro, as a village place and residences for livestock households in those areas.

NEW CASTLE (BELL). It is located in the territory of the former Zhdanov collective farm of Kungiro district. This fortress was built in 1946 by a detachment of the Khorezm expedition. In 1957, Khorezm T. A. The detachment led by Zhdanko researched his plan and V. N. Yagodin and N. I. Igonin and the structure of the castle were built by A. V. Gudkova wrote .

The new fortress was built around 1897 during the reign of Khiva Khan Madireim Khan.

The fortress was built by an Uzbek craftsman from Khiva, but the workers were Karakalpaks. His duties were varied. The mayor and the judge and their governing council are located here. They controlled the population around them. There were always 30-40 volunteer troops belonging to the Karakalpak tribe and Yasovulbashi in the fortress. It was necessary for them to protect the fortress from the Turkmens and to follow the people who went from Khojayli to Kungirat and from Kungirat to Khojayli. According to the residents of Kungiro district, the Turkmens have been constantly attacking. Therefore, constant guards were posted in the corner towers to monitor the movements of the Turkmens. Archaeologists discovered in 1957 that the New Castle was clearly designed with gates on each wall. On the eastern wall there was a gate for

people coming from Khojaly, and the entrance to Küngirat was divided by the western gate. The streets of these gates intersected with the street of the northern and southern gates in the castle.

The umbilical canal runs along the northern wall. Goods entered the fortress from the northern gate.

There was no permanent market, but there were many shops, especially brick shops. They sell meat, tea, sugar, butter. There is no exact time for wholesale. With the money from the sale, the shop owners buy fighting cock, alfalfa, grain, sesame seeds. Merchants lived in black houses.

They came from Khiva, Urganch, Khanka, permanent residents. Merchants came once a year in large ships. They were Uzbeks by nationality, but here they hire local people to trade, who trade for them with interest. In addition to volunteer troops and merchants, artisans and farmers lived in the fort. The peasants who lived in the castle were subordinate to the elder. Among the artisans in the castle were shoemakers and jewelers, blacksmiths, carriage makers, blacksmiths.

The difference between this city-fortress and other monuments is that it does not have a defensive moat. The new castle was created in the second half of the 19th century, in the former castle of Esengeldi. At the end of the 19th century, New Castle was the residence of Qabul Beglar Beg. This is the main governor of the Karakalpaks in the northern region. It should be noted that in the 19th century, the caravans going from Khiva to Orenburg passed through the desert and ascended the Ustyurt plateau to the territory of the New Castle fortress. L. about the new fortress. S. Berg. He writes that "in 1882, New Castle was flooded with water from Amudarya, and then the city fell apart". It should be noted that in general, the Karakalpak fortress in the studied period mainly served the purpose of protecting the population from external enemies. Battle towers and wall openings are characteristic of ancient fortresses associated with the origin of Karakalpak architecture and medieval fortresses of Khorezm.

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